

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. KRESTER M. DIAZ

Assistant Professor IV

Negros Oriental State University

kresterm Diaz@gmail.com

“WHISPERS OF A MOTHER’S VALOR”

This essay aims to examine how the main character’s personality in the short story, Heroic Mother by Hoa Pham, is portrayed and represented through analyzing the text’s linguistic features in the light of Transitivity theory as proposed by M.A.K Halliday.

The story, Heroic Mother, is a first-person narrative in which the main character portrays as the narrator and recalls the memories and victories she experienced during a war as a way to educate younger generations. This essay specifically analyzes that part of the story when the mother, a war survivor, starts to relive a moment of her post-traumatic war story.

The Text

- (1) I would go around the American soldiers begging for money and singing to them off key and off tempo.
- (2) Everyone thought I was crazy except my comrades at the National Liberation Front.
- (3) They knew I was carrying documents for them, in my pockets close to my skin.
- (4) I did not bathe, I stank so no one would want to go near me.
- (5) Sometimes it was fun acting crazy. (6) Sometimes I thought I would go crazy when I saw the bodies of my sisters, raped and tortured by the Imperial puppet forces.
- (7) Sometimes I was so scared acting crazy was my only escape.
- (8) Nowadays I am a kindly grandmother and I can be myself, silver haired and slightly senile. (9) I choose what I hear and say.
- (10) I chop meat with a cleaver ignoring the thunks in my head when I sometimes flashback to seeing the bodies of corpses splayed open, blood and bone. (11) We are all blood and bone in the end.
- (12) Sometimes at night I wake up and find myself downstairs. (13) My daughter would be holding my hand telling me to shut up.
- (14) “You are acting crazy again. (15) Remembering the war again. (16) It’s over.” (17) She would tell me off impatiently when it happened too often.
- (18) Then I see the TV news and try and look away. (19) The Americans invading Iraq are installing more puppet forces.
- (20) They say I’ve acted crazy all my life. (21) At least I don’t start wars, the only war I had was in my heart and disguised as a crazy woman. (22) All I could do was sing louder.

(Pham, 2008)

Analysis

For the fuller understanding of this chosen literary piece for analysis and appreciation of the writer's artistic achievement, I will use Burton's (1996) strategy:

- a) isolate the processes per se, and find which participants (who or what) is 'doing' each process;
- b) find what sorts of process they are, and which participant is engaged in which type of process; and
- c) find who or what is affected by each of these processes.

Based on the given text, I will abstract out the Actors in each process and spell out the lexical realization of each of the processes associated with them:

Sentence No	Actor	Process	Types of Process
1a	persona	would go	material-action-intention
b	persona	was begging	material-action-intention
c	persona	was singing	material-action-intention
2a	Everyone	thought	mental-cognition
b	persona	was	relational
3a	They	knew	mental cognition
b	persona	was carrying	material-action-intention
4a	persona	did not bathe	material-action-intention
b	persona	stank	material-action-intention
c	no one	would want to go	material-action-intention
5	-	was	relational
6a	person	thought	mental cognition
b	persona	would go	material-action-intention
c	persona	saw	mental cognition
d	the sisters	were raped and tortured	material-action-intention
7a	persona	was	relational
b	acting crazy	was	relational
8a	persona	am	relational
b	persona	can be	relational
9a	persona	choose	material-action-intention
b	persona	hear	perception
10a	persona	chop	material-action-intention
b	persona	flashback	mental cognition
11	We	are	relational
12a	persona	wake up	material-action-intention
b	persona	find	material-action-intention
13	My daughter	would be holding	material-action-intention
14	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
15	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
16	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
17a	She	would tell...off	material-action-intention
b	-	happened	material-action-intention
18a	persona	see	perception
b	persona	try	material-action-intention
c	persona	look away	material-action-intention

19a	The Americans	are installing	material-action-intention
b	The Americans	are invading	material-action-intention
20a	They	say	material-action-intention
b	persona	have acted	material-action-intention
21a	persona	don't start	material-action-intention
b	persona	had	material-action-relational
c	persona	disguised	material-action-intention
22a	persona	could do	material-action-intention
b	All	was	relational

This section of the analysis presents a clear, general picture of who is doing what and when in the persona's description of the 'world' around her. It is interesting to note that the persona is the dominant participant in 27 processes (clauses 1a-b-c, 2b, 3b, 4a-b, 6a-b-c, 7a, 8a-b, 9a-b, 10a-b, 12a-b, 18a-b-c, 20b, 21a-b-c, 22a) out of 44 or 61%. In the 27 processes, the persona is the one performing all actions. This tells the readers what the persona did just to survive the war by sharing her unforgettable past. Obviously, she is not only the main character but also the narrator of the story.

The persona is the participant in material-action-intention as evident in 20 clauses (1a-b-c, 3b, 4a-b, 6b-d, 9a, 10a, 12a-b, 18a-b-c, 20b, 21a-b-c, and 22a). 3 clauses for mental cognition (6a-c, 10b), 4 clauses for relational process (2b, 7a, 8a-b), and 2 clauses for perception (9b, 18a). The much greater use of material-action-intention shows the persona's active involvement in the past like when she mentioned of 'going around the American soldiers to beg for money and sing to them', 'carried documents for her comrades, and 'not bathing so no one would go near her'.

Then there is a shift of tense to indicate her present activities telling the readers that she still does a lot of things by herself and is surely not a weak grandma for she can still 'chop meat' and smart enough to 'choose what to hear and say' which proves that she still controls her internal and external processes without anyone dictating her. Apart of her traumatic war experience, in clause 13, the persona appears a co-participant with her daughter who held her hand telling her to shut up when the persona wakes up and finds herself downstairs at night. This I consider a very heartbreaking scene to imagine. Though in her narration she seems a very strong and smart woman, the main character as I observed, really suffered a post-traumatic stress disorder and depression. Good thing the daughter stays beside her to give her adequate physical and emotional support she needs.

This next analysis shows **who or what is affected by each process** in order for the readers to fully understand the persona's abstract reality of the world.

1 a	persona affects o by intention process
b	persona affects the American soldiers by intention process
c	persona affects the American soldiers by intention process
2 a	everyone affects the persona by mental cognition
b	persona affects everyone by relational process
3 a	persona's comrades affect o by mental cognition
b	persona affects o by intention process
4 a	persona affects o by intention process
b	persona affects o by intention process
c	no one affects the persona by intention process
5	o affects the environment by relational process

6 a	persona affects o by mental cognition
b	persona affects o by intention process
c	persona affects o by mental cognition
d	persona's sisters affect persona by mental cognition
7 a	persona affects o by relational process
b	persona affects o by relational process
8 a	persona affects o by relational process
b	personal affects o by relational process
9 a	persona affects o by intention process
b	persona affects o by perception
10 a	persona affects meat by intention process
b	persona affects o by intention process
11	people (we) affect o by relational process
12 a	persona affects o by intention process
b	persona affects o by intention process
13	persona affects persona's body part by intention process
14	n.a.
15	n.a.
16	n.a.
17 a	daughter affects persona by intention process
b	o affects the environment by intention process
18 a	persona affects o by perception
b	persona affects o by intention process
c	persona affects o by intention process
19 a	Americans affect o by intention process
b	Americans affect Iraq by intention process
20 a	people (they) affect persona by intention process
b	persona affects people by intention process
21 a	persona affects o by intention process
b	persona affects o by relational process
c	persona affects o by intention process
22 a	persona affects o by intention process
b	persona affects o by intention process

Analyzing the skeleton gives us a firmer grasp of the abstract reality of the persona's world. It is worth noting that the persona herself did a lot of intentional strategic plans to affect the American soldiers and the environment during the difficult days of her youth. She begged for money and sang to them without the soldier's knowledge that she was carrying some documents with her. She was stinky most of the days so no one would get near her. She acted crazy as a way of escape, so she would be ignored nor get raped and tortured. In other clauses, the persona affect nobody which reveals that all her actions were not influenced not dictated by anyone but her alone. She did all those on purpose and that is obviously for her protection.

Her past experience is undeniably a real tough nut to crack that the younger generation should recognize and be educated about these survivors' stories of their struggle for freedom, sacrifice, and patriotism.

However, at present, when she remembers all these again too often, the people around her think that she has a mental health problem (in clauses 14, 15, and 16). In my personal analysis, what she needs are people who will give her time to listen to her story and support her and not to think that

she is crazy. She might think that the war is still not over yet because most people still consider her as a crazy woman especially when she still sees round-the-clock news coverage of some horrific images of war here and there (in clause 18a-b-c). Ignoring her feelings will surely slow her recovery. Thus, her environment should help lessen these traumatic effects, recover her emotional equilibrium and regain control of her life once again.

Classroom Follow-up

I would suggest that for the students to feel and empathize the persona's suffering and loneliness, they have to rewrite the story using the third-person omniscient point of view. With this, the students would know and understand the thoughts and feelings of all of the characters, the main character, the American soldiers, and the main character's daughter while staying as close to the words/storyline of the original text as possible. In this activity, students would be so involved with the development of the main character's story. Another activity is for the students to offer some interpretations by putting themselves in the main character's shoes by answering the hypothetical question in a poem, *If you were the persona, would you also do the same thing (acting crazy etc) during war?*